

Recent Applications of Remote sensing in Agriculture-A Review

Maram Bhargav Reddy¹ and Dumpapenchala Vijayreddy²

^{1,2} College of Post Graduate Studies in Agricultural Sciences, CAU(I), Umiam, Meghalaya-793103.

Received 02/08/2023
Accepted for
publication 05/08/2023
Published on line
05/08/2023

Cite as

Abstract

Remote sensing is becoming a crucial technology in current agricultural practices, with several uses and benefits for farmers, researchers and policymakers. Crop monitoring and management are the principal applications of remote sensing in agriculture. Remote sensing allows for the rapid and precise diagnosis of crop health, growth and yield estimation by evaluating data received from satellites or airborne platforms. This data assists farmers in optimising irrigation, fertilization, pest and disease control measures, resulting in better resource allocation, enhanced productivity and lower environmental consequences. The identification and mapping of crop diseases and pests is a key application. Remote sensing may detect minute differences in plant physiology, such as chlorophyll content changes, which may signal the presence of diseases or pest infestations. Initial identification allows for focused treatments such as precision pesticide application, disease avoidance and crop loss reduction. Precision agriculture relies heavily on remote sensing. Farmers may produce precise field maps that delineate differences in soil qualities, nutrient levels, and moisture content by integrating satellite photography, GPS navigation systems and computer algorithms. This data enables site-specific management, allowing farmers to deploy resources precisely where they are required, optimising inputs, lowering costs and minimising environmental consequences. Remote sensing makes land-use planning and monitoring easier. It can assist in identifying potential agricultural sites, assessing land degradation and tracking changes in land cover and land use trends over time. Policymakers can use this data to make informed decisions about land management, sustainable agriculture practices and conservation activities. It helps with agricultural water resource management. It is feasible to monitor water availability, assess irrigation demands and identify locations vulnerable to drought or water stress by studying satellite data. This information allows for more efficient water distribution, reducing water waste and improving water-use efficiency in agricultural activities. Remote sensing has numerous uses in agriculture, revolutionizing old farming practices.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Precision agriculture, Remote sensing, Satellites, Spectral reflectance, Sustainability

Introduction:

The ever-increasing population and urbanization are leading pressure on limited natural resources that are available for the production. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) prioritize achieving global food security. This goal seeks to boost sustainable agriculture production, reduce food losses and waste, enhance nutrition, and end all forms of hunger. With a global population of 7.5 billion, 700 million people still lack access to food. By 2050, the world's food output must increase by 50% to meet demand.

This will require increasing farmland acreage and irrigation water use, which currently accounts for almost two-thirds of the world's water supplies.

Food security is a major challenge in many nations, especially developing countries. This is due to a number of factors, including poor resource management, inadequate laws governing the use of food and irrigation water, climate change, and land degradation.

Climate change is expected to further impact crop yields, making it difficult to manage food and water systems. Extreme events such as

floods and droughts can affect food availability, access to safe food, food prices, and sustainable food use. Climate change can also lead to prolonged droughts, increased reliance on groundwater, and a shift from irrigated to rainfed agricultural systems. Excessive watering can lead to crop lodging, salinity, and stunted crop growth. Pests and diseases can also significantly reduce agricultural yields. To increase productivity per unit area, farmers are adopting high-input agriculture, which can create problems for natural resources, the environment, and human health.

Therefore, there is a need for monitoring agriculture production systems to ensure that they are sustainable and do not harm the environment. Sustainable agricultural practices, improved irrigation and storage systems, and crop varieties that are resistant to floods and droughts are essential to addressing these challenges. By taking these steps, we can help to ensure food security for all.

Food security is a complex issue that requires both spatial and temporal management of crops. Traditional methods for monitoring crops are often labor-intensive and time-consuming. Remote sensing is a powerful tool that can be used to provide more accurate and timely information about crops.

Remote sensing is the acquisition of information about an object or area from a distance, typically from an aircraft or satellite. The use of remote sensing in agriculture is growing rapidly, as the technology becomes more affordable and accessible.

There are a number of satellites that are specifically designed for agricultural applications, and these satellites provide high-resolution data that can be used to monitor crops at a variety of scales. Remote sensing can be used to improve food security in a number of ways. For example, it can be used to: Identify areas of the cropland that are at risk of drought or flooding, monitor crop health and identify areas that are affected by pests or diseases, assess crop yields and identify areas that are underproducing, Plan irrigation and fertilizer applications, manage water resources, Track changes in land use and vegetation cover, Study the impact of climate change on agriculture.

Remote sensing is a powerful tool that can be used to improve food security. As the technology continues to develop, it is likely that its use in agriculture will become even more widespread.

What is remote sensing:

Satellite remote sensing is a technology that uses electromagnetic radiation to collect data about the Earth's surface. It emerged as a successor to aerial remote sensing in the 1960s, with the launch of the Explorer, TIROS (Television Infrared Observation Satellite), Corona and Landsat missions.

The process of satellite remote sensing begins when electromagnetic radiation interacts with the Earth's surface, either from the Sun or from the satellite itself. The radiation is reflected, absorbed, or transmitted and the Satellite sensors take measurements of the amount of radiation that is reflected. This reflected radiation contains data about the terrestrial activities that are currently happening at the location of the satellite overpass.

Terrestrial processes encompass hydrological cycle components, vegetation processes, associations with water bodies, geomorphology and topography. Each of these procedures may be responsive to electromagnetic radiation measurements only at particular wavelengths or frequencies. Therefore, it is important to locate satellite sensors that are suitable for the task of monitoring a particular terrestrial process.

In addition to the wavelength or frequency of the radiation, the spatial, temporal, spectral, and radiometric resolutions of the satellite sensor also influence the quality of the data that is collected. Spatial resolution refers to the size of the smallest object that can be detected by the sensor. Temporal resolution refers to revisit time for images are collected. Spectral resolution refers to the number of different wavelengths or frequencies of radiation that the sensor can measure. Radiometric resolution refers to the accuracy with which the sensor can measure the amount of radiation that is reflected. The development of satellite remote sensing has revolutionized the way that we monitor the Earth's surface.

Satellite sensors record reflected radiation spanning the electromagnetic spectrum at multiple wavelengths. These wavelengths are normally range from visible/optical (0.4–0.7 μm wavelength), infrared (IR) (0.7–1.3 μm , 1.3–3.0 μm , and 3.0–14 μm wavelengths), and microwave (1 mm–1 m wavelength). This section contains a list of satellite sensors (Table 1) as well as information on their duration, geographic and temporal resolutions.

Table 1: Comprehensive overview of the different types of satellite sensors and their capabilities

Sensor name	Wavelength range	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution
Landsat (Multispectral Scanner System (MSS))	500 nm - 1.1 μm (4 for Landsat 1,2,3, 4, and 5)	57 m, or 60 m	18 days, 16 days
Satellite pour l' Observation de la Terre (SPOT)	High Resolution Visible (HRV): 500 nm - 900 nm. High Resolution Visible and Infra-red (HRVIR) 500 nm - 1.75 μm	20 m 20 m; 10 m	26 days 26 days
IKONOS	Multispectral Sensor; Panchromatic Sensor 445 - 900 nm	3.2 m, 0.82 m	3 days
Terra, Aqua	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS), 400 nm - 14.4 μm	250 m, 500 m, and 1 km	16 days
QuickBird	Multispectral Sensor; Panchromatic Sensor 450 - 900 nm	2.62 m, 0.65 m	1 - 3.5 days
ENVISAT	Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer Instrument (MERIS) 390 - 1040 nm	300 m; 1200 m	35 days

RADARSAT-2	Synthetic Aperture Radar (C-band) 5.405 GHz (1)	3-100 m	24 days
TerraSAR-X	SAR-X 9.65 GHz (1)	1.1 m (SPOTLIGHT); 3.3 m (STRIPMAP); 18.5 m (SCANSAR)	11 days
RISAT-1	C Band Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) 5.35 GHz (1)	1 - 50 m	25 days
Sentinel 1A and 1B C-band	Synthetic Aperture Radar 5.405 GHz	5 m × 5 m (strip map mode), 5 m × 20 m (interferometric wide swath mode), and 25 m × 100 m (extra-wide swath mode); 5 m × 20 m (wave mode)	12 days

Applications of RS in agriculture:

RS is a valuable tool for farmers and agricultural professionals to monitor crop growth, health, and estimate yields, aiding in better crop management decisions. It can also map soil properties, optimize fertilizer and irrigation practices, monitor water resources, identify pests and diseases, and implement control measures early. RS can also be used for land use planning, climate change adaptation, and precision agriculture, enabling better decision-making and increased yields and profits. Overall, RS is a valuable resource for farmers and agricultural professionals, enhancing their crop management strategies and overall agricultural success.

Crop type and health:

Remote sensing can be used to identify different types of crops and to assess their health. The different crops have different reflectance's which are known as spectral signatures. The identification of crops helps in maintaining of crop inventory, yield prediction, crop rotation of area and sustainable management practices. Accurate crop categorization and mapping is essential for sustainable land management. The mapping of the crops requires the best input data and classifier method, especially in regions with limited field data. We use two-step processing chain that uses the intra-annual variance of temporal signals from remotely sensed data and prior knowledge of crop calendars to categorize crops. First, we used different soft wares (SNAP, ERDAS, QGIS, Arc Map) to preprocess and analyze data received from the various platforms that capture within-season phenological variation. We then modeled the developmental stage of each crop using a create training samples. Second, we tested a number of classification techniques, including support vector machines, random forest, and decision fusion. The classification accurate up to 85 to 95 %. The crop yield is estimate by semi empirical models by correlating the vegetation indices (NDVI, EVI, SAVI (Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index) and GVI (Green Vegetation Index)) and biophysical parameters (LAI and biomass) and empirical crop models.

The crop monitor is important to assess the impact of crop health. The health is mainly influenced by abiotic (water stress, environmental factors) and biotic factors (pest, weeds and diseases). The spectral reflectance of the crops varies when there is stress. The temporal profile of infected crop is less when compared to health crop. Diseases and pests can damage crops in four ways: by reducing biomass, developing lesions or pustules, destroying leaf pigments, or wilting plants. These pests and diseases can be detected by remote sensing at the leaf, canopy, and regional scales. Satellite remote sensing in optical and near-infrared (NIR) frequencies is routinely utilized on a regional scale to detect pests and diseases.

Fluorescence and microwave sensors have also been utilized for this kind of work, but most research have been confined to the leaf or canopy scale. Landsat, MODIS, Hyperion, and SPOT data, as well as information from multispectral and hyperspectral satellite sensors, have been proven to be useful for pest and disease identification. In addition to the commonly used vegetation indices, such as NDVI (Normalized Differential Vegetation Index), EVI (Enhanced Vegetation Index), NDWI (Normalized Differential Water Index), and LAI (Leaf Area Index), other indices have been proposed for pest and disease detection, such as the Disease Water Stress Index (DWSI) (Apan et al. 2004), Disease Index (DI) (Zheng et al., 2018), Yellow Rust Index (YRI) (Huang et al. 2014), Aphid Index (AI) (Luo et al. 2013), and Leafhopper Index (LHI) (Prabhakar et al. 2011).

These indices can be used to identify areas of the crop that are affected by pests or diseases, which can help farmers to take action to prevent further damage. Remote sensing is a valuable tool for pest and disease management, and it is likely to become even more important in the future as the demand for food production increases. Weeds are plants that compete with crops for nutrients and water, and can reduce crop productivity by up to 34% (Oerke 2006). Weeds can be detected using remote sensing, which can help farmers to identify and control weeds more effectively. Early studies used satellite sensors such as SPOT, Landsat TM, and AVHRR to identify weed-infested areas. However, these sensors have relatively coarse spatial resolution, which can make it difficult to detect small or patchy weeds.

More recently, researchers have used high-resolution satellite sensors such as QuickBird, Sentinel-2A, Landsat 8, SPOT-5, and Worldview-2 to detect weeds (Castillejo-Gonzalez et al. 2014). These sensors can provide reflectance information at very high spatial resolution (< 10 m), which makes it possible to identify individual weeds or small weed patches. In addition to using satellite sensors, researchers have also used vegetation indices to detect weeds. Vegetation indices are mathematical combinations of spectral reflectance bands that can be used to quantify the health and vigor of vegetation. Some vegetation indices that have been used for weed detection include NDVI, EVI, and NDWI.

Irrigation:

The ability to monitor irrigation on a wide scale is provided by satellite remote sensing. While monitoring irrigation, our primary research focuses on three elements.

a) Mapping of Irrigated area:

Optical satellite sensors are used to detect irrigation by analyzing the spectral patterns of irrigated and non-irrigated areas. These sensors can detect the difference in spectral reflectance between irrigated and non-irrigated areas, which can be used to classify irrigated and non-irrigated areas. In addition to spectral pattern analysis, optical satellite sensors can also be used to assess spatio-temporal variations of irrigation patterns by comparing images over time. This can be used to identify areas that are irrigated more or less frequently, which can help to improve water management. Accurate mapping of irrigated areas is essential for several reasons. First, it can help to ensure that water is allocated efficiently. Second, it can help to improve understanding of the water budget. Third, it can help to improve crop and hydrological models.

b) Quantification of irrigation water:

Quantifying irrigation water at large scales is challenging due to limited spatiotemporal information, technological and regulatory limitations, and the heterogeneity of agricultural systems. Irrigation estimates can be subject to substantial uncertainty due to the different practices used in different agricultural systems. Two techniques are used to calculate irrigation water usage: estimating irrigation water requirements (IWR) and estimating irrigation water consumption (IWU). IWR measures the difference between the quantity of water needed to regulate crop evapotranspiration losses (CWR) and effective precipitation (P). IWU measures the actual amount of water applied to crops. IWR is a useful tool for planning irrigation systems and managing water resources. However, it is important to note that IWR estimates can be inaccurate due to the variability of CWR and P. IWU is a more accurate measure of irrigation water usage, but it is more difficult to obtain.

c) Estimating irrigation water consumption (IWU) from soil moisture data:

Irrigation withdrawals from the source are often estimated, but they may not accurately reflect actual irrigation consumption due to under- or over-irrigation. Recent studies have focused on using soil moisture fluctuations in precipitation data to estimate IWU. The SM2RAIN method (Brocca et al. 2018; Jalilvand et al. 2019), which is applied to soil moisture products, has been used to quantify IWU by calculating the systematic discrepancies between precipitation from satellite soil moisture products and actual precipitation data. Other studies have attempted to calculate IWU by calculating the discrepancy between simulations of soil moisture produced by land surface models and simulations produced by including satellite soil moisture into land surface models.

Rootzone soil moisture measurement is essential for reliable IWU estimates. Rootzone soil moisture is the amount of water in the soil that is available to plants. By measuring rootzone soil moisture, it is

possible to track how much water is being used by plants and how much water is being lost to evaporation or drainage. Here are some additional examples of how remote sensing is being used in agriculture:

Precision Agriculture:

Remote sensing is critical in precision agriculture because it provides vital information on crops, soil conditions, and environmental elements. These are some significant remote sensing usages for precision agriculture:

a) Crop Monitoring:

Remote sensing enables growers to assess crop health and development across wide areas. Crop vigour, growth stages, and stress conditions can all be determined using satellite or aerial images. This information assists farmers in identifying areas that require care, like as nutrient deficits, pest infestations, or irrigation issues (Khanal et al. 2017; Hunt and Daughtry 2018).

b) Yield Prediction:

Growers can anticipate crop yields before harvest by analysing the data from remote sensing during the growing season. Predictive models for crop production can be constructed through the integration of data on vegetation indices, weather conditions, and historical yield data (Sishodia et al. 2020). This enables growers to make more informed decisions about storage, marketing, and financial planning.

c) Detection of Crop diseases and Pest Infestations:

Remote sensing can detect crop diseases and infestations of pests in advance, enabling prompt action. Sensors that detect slight variations in crop reflectance patterns caused by diseases or pests are known as hyperspectral or multispectral sensors. This information enables growers to execute customised treatment tactics, decreasing pesticide consumption and crop losses (Kumawat et al. 2023).

d) Soil mapping and management:

Remote sensing can help with the mapping of soil and characterisation by providing vital information about soil types, moisture content, and nutrient levels. Growers can create comprehensive soil maps and make accurate judgements on fertiliser application, irrigation timing, and farming practises by combining the data from remote sensing with ground-based measurements (Rebouh et al. 2023).

f) Irrigation Management:

Data from remote sensing, like thermal photography, can assist growers in optimising watering practises. Remote sensing allows farmers to identify the best times and locations to irrigate by assessing crop water stress levels, evapotranspiration rates, and soil moisture content. This ensures effective water usage and minimises water waste (Samreen et al. 2023).

g) Weed Detection and Management:

Weed infestations in agriculture fields can be identified by using remote sensing techniques. Farmers may discern between crops and weeds by analysing high-resolution pictures, allowing for tailored herbicide administration. This method reduces herbicide use while minimising environmental effect (Saranya et al. 2023).

h) Variable rate application:

Remote sensing data can be used to guide variable rate application of fertilisers, herbicides, and other resources. Farmers can administer inputs in a site-specific manner by analysing regional changes in crop health, nutrient deficits, or insect threats. This method optimises resource utilisation, lowers costs, and reduces environmental effect (Kumawat et al. 2023).

Disaster management:

Remote sensing is essential in many facets of disaster management. It entails gathering information about the Earth's surface by collecting and analysing data from aerial or spaceborne sensors. Here are some significant remote sensing applications in disaster management:

a) Damage Assessment:

Remote sensing aids in determining the degree and severity of natural catastrophe damage caused by earthquakes, hurricanes, floods, and wildfires. Authorities use satellite data and aerial photographs to compare pre and post-disaster circumstances, allowing them to identify affected areas, estimate damage, and prioritise response activities (Calantropio et al. 2018).

b) Emergency Response Planning:

Remote sensing data is useful for emergency response planning. It aids in the identification of vulnerable locations, such as flood-prone zones, landslide-prone areas, or places prone to forest fires. This knowledge enables officials to properly design evacuation plans, assign resources, and mobilise reaction squads (Damasevicius et al. 2023).

c) Hazard Mapping and Risk Assessment:

By identifying and mapping possible dangers, remote sensing aids in hazard mapping and risk assessment (Alarifi et al. 2022). It aids in the monitoring and analysis of elements such as land use, vegetation cover, slope stability, and water bodies, all of which are critical for assessing risk and identifying regions vulnerable to particular types of disasters.

d) Early warning systems:

Remote sensing data is utilised to construct early warning systems for a variety of calamities. Satellite-based sensors, for example, can monitor weather patterns, detect cyclones, and follow their movement, allowing for early warnings. Remote sensing can also be used to monitor river levels, detect changes in volcanic activity, or spot symptoms of an imminent landslide, allowing early warnings to be delivered to vulnerable people (Abdalzاهر et al. 2023).

e) Flood monitoring and management:

Remote sensing techniques such as Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) and LiDAR can measure flood extent, monitor water levels, and estimate flood damage. This data aids in disaster response coordination, evacuation planning, and flood risk management (Sharma et al. 2019).

f) Forest Fire Detection and Monitoring:

Satellite photography is utilised to identify and track the progression of forest fires. Sensors that identify temperature anomalies and changes in vegetation health give real-time data to fire mitigation organisations, enabling them to prioritise firefighting activities and properly deploy resources (Tran et al. 2020).

g) Post-Disaster Recovery and Reconstruction:

Remote sensing aids in the recovery and rehabilitation activities following a disaster. High-resolution imaging aids in the identification of ideal areas for temporary shelters, the assessment of infrastructure damage, and the monitoring of rehabilitation work. During the rehabilitation phase, this information aids decision-making and the distribution of resources (Ghaffarian et al. 2021). Disaster management authorities can improve their preparedness, response, and recovery capacities by employing remote sensing technologies, reducing the effect of disasters and saving lives.

Climate change research

Remote sensing is critical in climate change research because it provides useful data and insights into numerous parts of the Earth's

climate system. Here are some significant remote sensing applications in climate change research:

a) Monitoring Atmospheric Composition:

Remote sensing devices, such as satellites fitted with spectrometers, can be used to determine the chemical composition of the Earth's atmosphere. They collect information on greenhouse gases (such as carbon dioxide and methane), aerosols, ozone, and other trace gases (Wei et al. 2020). The results of these tests aid researchers in understanding fluctuations in atmospheric composition, tracking greenhouse gas sources and sinks, and assessing their effect on global warming.

b) Land Surface Change Observation:

Remote sensing offers information on land cover, land use change, and vegetation dynamics. Satellite imagery aids in the monitoring of deforestation, urbanisation, agricultural practises, and changes in vegetation production. This information is critical for comprehending the function of land surface changes in climate systems like the carbon cycle, albedo impact, and water cycle (Hussain and Karuppannan 2023).

c) Climate Simulation Validation and Calibration:

Climate models are validated and calibrated using remote sensing data. Satellite measurements are a useful tool for evaluating the correctness of model simulations, notably with regard to of air temperature, moisture, and cloud cover. These comparisons help boost the predictability and dependability of climate models (Sun et al. 2023).

d) Carbon Monitoring: Remote

sensing technologies aid carbon cycle research by assessing vegetation biomass and production. Satellite and aerial sensor data can be used to assess vegetation carbon stocks, follow forest changes, and predict carbon dioxide fluxes across the land surface and the atmosphere. This data contributes to an improved comprehension of carbon dynamics and the function of terrestrial ecosystems in the global carbon cycle (Jiao et al. 2021).

Climate researchers can improve their awareness of climate change processes, detect movements and trends, and promote evidence-based decision-making for adaptation and mitigation measures by using data from satellite observations.

Challenges of Remote sensing in agriculture:

Data availability and accessibility: Remote sensing data can be expensive and difficult to obtain, especially in developing countries. Additionally, the data may not be available in the right format or resolution for the specific application.

a. Data quality:

Remote sensing data can be affected by factors such as cloud cover, atmospheric conditions, and sensor noise. This can make it difficult to extract accurate information from the data.

b. Interpretation of data:

Remote sensing data can be complex to interpret, and there is often a high degree of uncertainty associated with the results. This can make it difficult to make informed decisions based on the data.

c. Lack of user skills and knowledge:

Remote sensing is a complex technology, and users need to have the skills and knowledge to interpret the data correctly. This can be a barrier to the adoption of remote sensing in agriculture.

d. Lack of integration with other data sources:

Remote sensing data is often used in isolation, but it can be more effective when it is integrated with other data sources, such as weather data, soil data, and crop yield data.

These are just some of the challenges of remote sensing in agriculture. However, there are also many potential benefits of using remote sensing, such as the ability to monitor crop health, assess crop yields, and map irrigation water use. As the technology continues to develop, these challenges are likely to be overcome, and remote sensing will become an increasingly important tool for agricultural management.

Future prospects of Remote sensing in agriculture:

Increased availability and accessibility of data: As the cost of RS data decreases and the availability of data increases, it will become easier for farmers and agriculturalists to use RS data to make informed decisions.

a. Improved data quality:

As RS sensors and data processing techniques improve, the quality of RS data will improve. This will make it easier to extract accurate information from the data and to make informed decisions based on the data.

b. Simplified data interpretation:

As RS software and tools become more user-friendly, it will be easier for farmers and agriculturalists to interpret RS data. This will make it easier for them to make informed decisions based on the data.

c. Increased integration with other data sources:

As RS data becomes more integrated with other data sources, such as weather data, soil data, and crop yield data, it will become more powerful tool for agricultural management.

d. New applications of RS:

As RS technology continues to develop, new applications for RS in agriculture will emerge. For example, RS could be used to monitor the impact of climate change on agriculture or to track the spread of pests and diseases.

These are just some of the future prospects of RS in agriculture. As the technology continues to develop, RS is likely to become an increasingly important tool for agricultural management.

Conclusion:

Remote sensing has the potential to revolutionize agriculture and help to ensure food security for a growing population. However, there are still some challenges that need to be addressed, such as the cost of data and the lack of user skills and knowledge. As these challenges are overcome, remote sensing is likely to become an essential tool for agricultural management. The future of remote sensing in agriculture is bright. As the technology continues to develop, remote sensing is likely to become an increasingly important tool for agricultural management.

Remote sensing data will become more widely available and affordable, making it easier for farmers and agriculturalists to use. Remote sensing sensors and data processing techniques will continue to improve, making it possible to extract more accurate and detailed information from the data. Remote sensing software and tools will become more user-friendly, making it easier for farmers and agriculturalists to interpret data and make informed decisions. Remote sensing will be more integrated with other data sources, such as weather data, soil data, and crop yield data.

This will make it possible to develop more comprehensive and accurate models of agricultural systems. Overall, the future of remote sensing in agriculture is bright. As the technology continues to develop, remote sensing is likely to become an increasingly important tool for agricultural management.

References

Abdalzaher MS, Elsayed HA, Fouda MM, Salim MM (2023) Employing machine learning and IoT for earthquake early

warning system in smart cities. *Energies* 16:495. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16010495>

Alarifi SS, Abdelkareem M, Abdalla F, Alotaibi M (2022) Flash flood hazard mapping using remote sensing and GIS techniques in southwestern Saudi Arabia. *Sustainability* 14:14145. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142114145>

Apan A, Held A, Phinn S, Markley J (2004) Detecting sugarcane 'orange rust' diseases using EO-1 Hyperion hyperspectral imagery. *Int J Remote Sens* 25:489-498. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431160310001618031>

Baumhoer CA, Dietz AJ, Dech S, Kuenzer C (2018) Remote sensing of Antarctic glacier and ice-shelf front dynamics-A review. *Remote Sensing* 10:1445. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs10091445>

Brocca L, Tarpanelli A, Filippucci P, Dorigo W, Zaussinger F, Gruber A, Prieto DF (2018) How much water is used for irrigation? A new approach exploiting coarse resolution satellite soil moisture products. *Int J Appl Earth Obs Geoinf* 73:752-766. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2018.08.023>

Calantropio A, Chiabrando F, Sammartano G, Spano A, Lose LT (2018) UAV strategies validation and remote sensing data for damage assessment in post-disaster scenarios. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences* 42:121-128. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-3-W4-121-2018>

Castillejo-Gonzalez IL, Pena-Barragan JM, Jurado-Exposito M, Mesas-Carrascosa FJ, Lopez-Granados F (2014) Evaluation of pixel-and object-based approaches for mapping wild oat (*Avena sterilis*) weed patches in wheat fields using QuickBird imagery for site-specific management. *Eur J Agron* 59:57-66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2014.05.009>

Damasevicius R, Bacanin N., Misra S (2023) From sensors to safety: Internet of Emergency Services (IoES) for emergency response and disaster management. *Journal of Sensor and Actuator Networks* 12(3): 41. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jsan12030041>

Ghaffarian S, Roy D, Filatova T, Kerle N (2021) Agent-based modelling of post-disaster recovery with remote sensing data. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 60:102285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2021.102285>

Huang W, Guan Q, Luo J, Zhang J, Zhao J, Liang D, Huang L, Zhang D (2014) New optimized spectral indices for identifying and monitoring winter wheat diseases. *IEEE J Sel Top Appl Earth Obs Remote Sens* 7:2516-2524. doi: 10.1109/JSTARS.2013.2294961.

Hunt ERJ, Daughtry, CS (2018) What good are unmanned aircraft systems for agricultural remote sensing and precision agriculture?. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*

- 39:5345-5376.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01431161.2017.1410300>
- Hussain S, Karuppanan S (2023) Land use/land cover changes and their impact on land surface temperature using remote sensing technique in district Khanewal, Punjab Pakistan. *Geology Ecology and Landscapes* 7:46-58. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24749508.2021.1923272>
- Jalilvand E, Tajrishy M, Hashemi SAGZ, Brocca L (2019) Quantification of irrigation water using remote sensing of soil moisture in a semi-arid region. *Remote Sens Environ* 231:111226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2019.111226>
- Janekovic I, Rayson MD, Jones NL, Watson P, Pattiaratchi C (2022) 4D-Var data assimilation using satellite sea surface temperature to improve the tidally-driven interior ocean dynamics estimates in the Indo-Australian Basin. *Ocean Modelling* 171:101969. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocemod.2022.101969>
- Jiao W, Wang L, McCabe MF (2021) Multi-sensor remote sensing for drought characterization: current status, opportunities and a roadmap for the future. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 256:112313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2021.112313>
- Khanal S, Fulton J, Shearer S (2017) An overview of current and potential applications of thermal remote sensing in precision agriculture. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 139:22-32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2017.05.001>
- Kumawat RK, Tiwari G, Ramakrishnan RS, Bhayal D, Debnath S, Thakur S, Bhayal L (2023) Remote Sensing Related Tools and their Spectral Indices Applications for Crop Management in Precision Agriculture. *International Journal of Environment and Climate Change* 13:171-188. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ijecc/2023/v13i11665>
- Luo J, Huang W, Zhao J, Zhang J, Zhao C, Ma R (2013) Detecting aphid density of winter wheat leaf using hyperspectral measurements. *IEEE J Sel Top Appl Earth Obs Remote Sens* 6:690-698. doi: 10.1109/JSTARS.2013.2248345
- Oerke EC (2006) Crop losses to pests. *The Journal of Agricultural Science* 144:31-43. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021859605005708>
- Prabhakar M, Prasad Y, Thirupathi M, Sreedevi G, Dharajothi B, Venkateswarlu B (2011) Use of ground based hyperspectral remote sensing for detection of stress in cotton caused by leafhopper (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae). *Comput Electron Agric* 79:189-198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2011.09.012>
- Rebouh NY, Mohamed ES, Polityko PM, Dokukin PA, Kucher DE, Latati M, Okeke SE, Ali MA (2023) Towards improving the precision agriculture management of the wheat crop using remote sensing: A case study in Central Non-Black Earth region of Russia. *The Egyptian Journal of Remote Sensing and Space Science* 26:505-517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrs.2023.06.007>
- Samreen T, Ahmad M, Baig MT, Kanwal S, Nazir MZ (2023) Remote Sensing in Precision Agriculture for Irrigation Management. *Environmental Sciences Proceedings* 23:31. <https://doi.org/10.3390/environsciproc2022023031>
- Saranya T, Deisy C, Sridevi S, Anbananthen KSM (2023) A comparative study of deep learning and Internet of Things for precision agriculture. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* 122:106034. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2023.106034>
- Sharma TPP, Zhang J, Koju UA, Zhang S, Bai Y, Suwal MK (2019) Review of flood disaster studies in Nepal: A remote sensing perspective. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 34:18-27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2018.11.022>
- Sishodia RP, Ray RL, Singh SK (2020) Applications of remote sensing in precision agriculture: A review. *Remote Sensing* 12:3136. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12193136>
- Sun M, Gong A, Zhao X, Liu N, Si L, Zhao S (2023) Reconstruction of a Monthly 1 km NDVI Time Series Product in China Using Random Forest Methodology. *Remote Sensing* 15:3353. Sun M, Gong A, Zhao X, Liu N, Si L, Zhao S (2023) Reconstruction of a Monthly 1 km NDVI Time Series Product in China Using Random Forest Methodology. *Remote Sensing* 15:3353.
- Tran DQ, Park M, Jung D, Park, S. (2020) Damage-map estimation using UAV images and deep learning algorithms for disaster management system. *Remote Sensing* 12:4169. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12244169>
- Wei X, Chang NB, Bai K, Gao, W (2020) Satellite remote sensing of aerosol optical depth: Advances, challenges, and perspectives. *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology* 50:1640-1725. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10643389.2019.1665944>
- Zhang X, Qiu J, Leng G, Yang Y, Gao Q, Fan Y, Luo, J (2018) The potential utility of satellite soil moisture retrievals for detecting irrigation patterns in China. *Water*, 10:1505. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w10111505>
- Zheng G, Muhammad S, Sattar A, Ballesteros-Canovas JA (2023) Cryospheric remote sensing. *Frontiers in Remote Sensing* 4:1204667. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsen.2023.1204667>